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Emergence and dissemination of carbapenem resistance *Acinetobacter baumannii* and toxic metals in an Urban receiving river system of Eastern India

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Antimicrobial resistance bacteria (ARB) and antimicrobial resistance genes (ARG) have been regarded as emerging environmental pollutants in the entire world as these are known to cause public health hazards. The untreated biomedical wastes from healthcare units as well as the water from domestic and municipal wastes, are the sink for these pollutants and are disseminated into the river. The contaminated river's surface water with these pollutants poses a risk to public health due to the possibility of human exposure via bathing, drinking, and mobility in the food chain. In addition, heavy metals, the other major anthropogenic pollutant of river water, are known to drive bacterial resistance to antibiotics. Water of any urban city has been accepted as the index of determination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) pollution load of any Urban city. No critical ethical issues are involved in conducting routine molecular surveillance and are considered safe to deal with. Therefore, understanding AMR pollution's state of the art is the utmost requisite before planning and designing their mitigation through biotransformation.

Carbapenem resistance *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CARB pollutant) is designated as the world health organization (WHO) top priority pathogens, and it threatens serious infections in tertiary care hospitals. These CARB pollutants have the ability to persists in diverse environments, including water bodies. Our preliminary surveillance study reveals the danger of environmental contamination of drug-resistant and virulent CRAB strains in the Kathajodi river. Our results provide information on assessing risks to public health posed by the contamination of CRAB pathogens and toxic metals.